

CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS OF ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF THE "MIZDAKHON" COMPLEX AND STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

This article contains information about the construction methods and materials of the monuments located in the Khojaeli District of the Republic of Karakalpakstan – in the complex “Mizdakhan”.

Among the countries of the world, there are very few countries that can be proud of their magnificent architectural structures. Along with the eternal cities of Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva, Tashkent, and Shakhrisabz, which are famous throughout the world and attract tourists from all over the world, we should be proud of the "Mizdakhan" complex in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, which has a history of almost 2500 years.

Therefore, it is our duty to study these architectural monuments created by our people and formed over centuries, to preserve them, and to provide them to present and future generations. We should bring to the attention of the wider public information about the history, current technical condition, and problems of ensuring the durability of magnificent architectural monuments located in the territory of ancient Khorezm and the Republic of Karakalpakstan (Southern Aral Sea region), which are a miracle of world architecture.

The Mizdakhan complex is located in the territory of ancient Khorezm (in the Khojaeli district of the present Republic of Karakalpakstan), only 25 km from the capital of the Khorezmshah Empire, Kuhna Urgench. This city was located on the Great Silk Road, and according to the Arab traveler al-Makdi, who visited here in 985, there were 1200 feudal fortresses in the Mizdakhan region at that time. Thus, in this city, along with science and enlightenment, architecture and construction were highly developed. As proof of this, it is natural that the construction style of the miraculous architectural monument "Nazlumkhan Suluv Mausoleum," dating back to the 12th century and located 10 meters below the ground in this area, and the construction materials used in it leave a great impression on everyone who sees it, as if it were a living history (Figures 1, 2).

a) above-ground door

b) underground entrance

Figure 1. Arched doors at the entrance of the "Nazlumkhan Suluv" mausoleum, located 10 m underground, dating back to the 12th century in the Mizdakkhan complex.

N.S.Grajdankina, who analyzed the composition and properties of building materials used in the Nazlumkhan Suluv architectural monument, proved through her scientific research that this monument is a historical monument of the 12th century [2]. The total land area of this monument, erected in a complex architectural plan, is 30x30 meters, and it is located 10 meters below ground. The height of the upper part of the monument visible from the ground is 5.10 meters. The height of the central large room is 10.60 meters (Fig. 2, a), which is covered with an octagonal dome. This room, covered with an arrow-shaped dome, that is, the underground part, is accessed by 20 steps (Fig. 1, b).

The dimensions of the main room of the architectural monument, where the saganas are located, are 7.5x7.5 meters, the dimensions of the rooms on both sides are 4.5x4.5 meters, and the height is 7.70 meters. These rooms contained 3 tombs, in which inscriptions in Arabic were written on marble slabs. High-quality fired bricks measuring 23.5x23.5x5 cm were used in the restoration of the architectural monument. The green "gulbantic" tiles used in ancient Khorezm architecture were skillfully laid on the walls of the rooms. Particularly, the carved stalactite-muqarnas (Figure 2, a) on the base of the dome, and the gold-plated patterns on the "Qiz" mausoleum testify to the high level of knowledge and skill of Khorezmian master architects of that time, as well as the development of their construction methods.

a)

б)

Figure 2. Located underground in Mizdakkhan Complex Interior of the architectural monument "Nazlumkhan Suluv" (a) and elements in the wall structure (b)

In each section of the axial octagonal dome structure, lighting windows are located, and the part under the dome is covered with solid tiled slabs. Wooden beams laid horizontally on the lower part of the lower wall of the interior rooms of the architectural monument at a height of 1.20 m increase the strength of the wall structure, and the metal pegs and decorative elements fastening them not only ensure the seismic resistance of the wall, but also add a special beauty to the room for centuries (Fig. 2, b).

Another remarkable masterpiece of the architecture of ancient Khorezm, dating back to the 11th-12th centuries, is the architectural monument of Khalifa Rajab in the Mizdakhan complex (Fig. 3, a). This monument may have been a madrasa or khanqah at that time, but now only three walls 16 meters high have survived. The plan of the monument is square-shaped, covered with a dome in the shape of a cube. Its portal and dome parts collapsed as a result of negative impacts over time.

All the structures of the monument - the foundation, walls, and roof - are made of baked bricks measuring 27.0x27.0x5.5 and 28.0x28.0x5.5 cm. One of the most beautiful structural elements of the architectural monument and very rare in the architectural and construction work of Central Asia, the stepped arched sails for the corners of the dome base are made of baked bricks measuring 40.0x40.0x7.0 cm.

On the base of the Khalifa Rajab architectural monument, reed deposits were laid, some parts of which decayed, but in some places the reeds have been well preserved for more than 1000 years. These reed deposits were widely used in the architectural and construction work of ancient Khorezm, as they not only served as waterproofing in the wall structure but also protected the brick layers from salinity. Reed deposits absorb capillary moisture, facilitating water evaporation, thereby reducing the crystalline effect of moisture entering the structure and the presence of salts. The craftsmen of that time were very well aware of this property of reeds and knew how to use them very skillfully.

In the Mizdakhan complex, a unique monument of the architecture of ancient Khorezm, dating back to the 13th century, is the mausoleum of Shamun Nabi (Fig. 3, b). This mausoleum measures 30x5.85 meters and is covered with spherical domes in the shape of a bakh made of baked bricks measuring 24x24x6 cm. The most interesting thing is that inside this mausoleum there is only one tomb, its dimensions are 25.31 x 1.30 m, and its height is 1.07 meters. Seven domes were built on top of this tomb.

a)

б)

Figure 3. Interior of the architectural mausoleum of Shamun Nabi "Khalifa Rajab"**(b) Bagal-sails at the monument (a)**

Today, this unique historical monument is in dire need of repair, because over the centuries and as a result of the change of seasons, any fortified structures - fortresses, architectural monuments - wear out, deteriorate, and deteriorate. Currently, in the territory of the Southern Aral Sea region, as a result of an increase in environmental emissions and a sharp change in the ecology, an increase in the amount of salt and dust in the air, an increase in salinity, and the growth of various harmful insects are accelerating the process of destruction of ancient Khorezm monuments.

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